

UTILIZING COGNITIVE TECHNIQUES TO ENHANCE PERFORMANCE IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS.

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ABSTRACT

Improving the professional training of managers in the field of physical education and sports today requires the need to use foreign experience in their preparation, especially for the experience of using cognitive psychology techniques in professional and personal training. The study of international experience training of future managers of physical education and sports is of great importance for the implementation of positive trends in higher education in terms of the quality of their training and the formation of their professional competence.

Keywords: education; cognitive application; physical education; sports; managers

In modern pedagogy, cognitive learning, along with recognized and well-known areas of learning, such as developmental, programmed, problematic and others, is becoming widespread in many countries. However, the tasks of cognitive learning in these countries are solved differently in accordance with their internal socio-economic and cultural-educational problems.

Cognitive approaches in teaching are aimed at the formation of critical thinking: the ability to distinguish between factual information and value judgments; the ability to distinguish between facts and assumptions; the ability to distinguish logical types of communication; the ability to highlight specific subject types of relationships; the ability to detect factual and logical errors in reasoning; the ability to distinguish material arguments from irrelevant; the ability to distinguish between reasonable and unfounded estimates, etc.

The main goal of cognitive learning is, according to researchers, the development of the entire set of mental abilities and strategies that make learning and adaptation to new situations possible. In our view, cognitive learning is not a

combination of various techniques, methods of learning, but a dynamic system based on a model of the individual's bio psychosocial organization. Such a learning system uses not only intellectual cognitive mechanisms that are implemented in traditional verbal teaching methods aimed at developing the reflective activity of students and the formation of intellectual skills necessary for solving educational problems, but primarily sensory-perceptual channels of various modalities, as well as sensually - Intuitive ways to gain new knowledge. The use of cognitive learning methods in our understanding allows us to combine the natural (subjective), subjective-mental and rational principles of the personality into a single whole through interconnected actions, discussions, thoughts and self-control, contributes to an increase in the effectiveness of cognitive development and the intellectual system as a whole. A distinctive feature of training is that the leading role is given to sensory-perceptual and emotionally-intuitive ways of acquiring knowledge.

These methods are active, allow you to reveal the procedural aspects of intelligence, contribute to the identification and development of hidden individual abilities of future managers of physical education and sports. The current field of creative professions has expanded significantly. Uncertainty, a constant change of conditions and an increase in risks, together with an increase in the requirements for productivity and labour efficiency, made all professions related to intellectual activity demanding on technology able to secure the development of a space of reliability and effectiveness of intellectual efforts.

But the field of higher education is extremely sensitive to the technologicalization of cognitive processes. The variety of cognitive processes involved in this area provides for a diverse multiplicity of cognitive technologies aimed at:

- the implementation of training;
- mental processes providing
- mastering new material;
- development of memory;
- the formation of cognitive experience of the personality of a specialist;
- cognitive development of personality and its self-improvement;
- the formation of cognitive mechanisms of control of intellectual activity;
- cognitive interactions in interactive and communication processes;
- cognitive technologies of joint cognitive and other (decision-making) project activities.

Now in most countries there is an integration of the sphere of physical education and sports in the market environment. This is due to factors such as the transition to a new form of modern society - information, when information is not only an important unit, but also the ability to operate and use it for one's own development, to consistently introduce high standards in education. This is required by the labor market, which sets new requirements for the academic disciplines taught in higher education institutions and, in general, for the quality of educational services. To a large extent, this is also associated with the opening of borders between countries and the integration of educational systems in the global educational space and, accordingly, the growing mobility of students.

The leading trend in the process of formation of professional competence of managers of physical education and sports in the world is that a modern manager must have a sufficient level of education for effective professional activity, be able to use the knowledge and information gained in practice, see real problems and find ways to overcome them, be able to think critically and in a non-standard way, project training, analyses professional activities and anticipate its consequences, be prepared for organizational and managerial work. In addition, he must have certain moral qualities formed: the ability to work with people, solve conflict situations, take responsibility for managerial decisions, be active, independent, ready to change his professional profile. The requirements for the manager of physical education and sports are considered, the tasks and principles of training these personnel are determined in accordance with the needs of the international labor market.

Theoretical analysis of pedagogical experience in improving the training of managers of physical culture and sports using cognitive training techniques in countries that have achieved some success in this field will allow it to be taken into account in the process of upgrading the vocational education system of the relevant profile. It is as a result of a comprehensive analysis of the system of training sports managers within the higher professional education of foreign countries, a real opportunity to use this experience to improve the training of these professionals and their professional competence in higher education institutions.

The basis of our work was the scientific achievements of leading scientists in the field of improving the psychological component of the professional training of sports students and sports managers. In particular, Sushchenko in her work described in detail the system for implementing cognitive techniques in the context of developing a professional and personal component.

Cognitive techniques play a crucial role in enhancing athletic performance and learning in physical education. These techniques help athletes and students improve concentration, mental resilience, decision-making, and overall performance. This article explores the application of cognitive techniques in the field of physical education and sports, backed by experiences and case studies.

The Role of Cognitive Techniques in Sports and Physical Education Cognitive techniques are mental strategies used to enhance focus, motivation, and performance in sports. These include visualization, self-talk, goal-setting, and mindfulness training. When applied effectively, these techniques contribute to improved skill acquisition, greater confidence, and enhanced performance under pressure.

Application in Physical Education

1. Visualization and Mental Rehearsal: Students practice movements and strategies in their minds before executing them physically. Helps in motor learning and coordination. Example: A basketball player visualizing free-throw shots before making an attempt.

2. Self-Talk and Positive Reinforcement: Encouraging students to use positive affirmations to build confidence. Helps in overcoming performance anxiety and developing a growth mindset. Example: A young gymnast telling themselves, "I can do this," before performing a routine.

3. Goal-Setting and Motivation: Setting short-term and long-term goals for skill improvement. Helps in maintaining focus and tracking progress. Example: A runner setting incremental goals to improve sprint times.

4. Mindfulness and Relaxation Techniques: Techniques such as deep breathing and meditation help in managing stress and anxiety. Enhances concentration and focus during performance. Example: A soccer player using deep breathing techniques before taking a penalty kick.

Application in Competitive Sports 1.Cognitive Restructuring for Performance Enhancement: Changing negative thoughts into positive ones to improve resilience.

Example: A tennis player shifting focus from mistakes to learning opportunities. 2. Reaction Time Training: Enhancing quick decision-making skills through cognitive exercises. Example: Video analysis and simulated game scenarios for football players.3.Team Cohesion and Communication: Mental strategies to improve teamwork and understanding among athletes. Example: Pre-game visualization of plays and strategies to build synchronization in a team.

Case Studies and Real-Life Experiences 1.High School Basketball Team: Implemented visualization techniques before games, resulting in a 15% improvement

in shooting accuracy. 2. Olympic Swimmers: Used guided imagery to simulate race conditions, reducing anxiety and improving reaction time off the blocks. 3. Youth Soccer Academy: Integrated self-talk and positive reinforcement, leading to increased confidence and better performance under pressure.

Conclusion: The application of cognitive techniques in physical education and sports has shown significant improvements in performance, motivation, and mental resilience. Whether in a school setting or professional athletics, incorporating mental training alongside physical training can lead to holistic development and success. Coaches, educators, and athletes should integrate cognitive techniques into regular training regimens to maximize their potential and enhance overall sports performance.

REFERENCES:

1. Исаева У., Джалилова С. The usage of new pedagogical technologies in lessons //Молодой ученый. – 2018. – №. 5. – С. 169-171.
2. Богиева Т. Р. Преимущества и недостатки применения традиционных и нетрадиционных методов преподавания иностранного языка в образовательных учреждениях СПО //Инновационная наука. – 2016. – №. 4-2 (16). – С. 139-141.
3. Mahsudova B. N. et al. Проблема межкультурной коммуникации в обучении иностранным языкам //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2018. – №. 1. – С. 76-79.
4. Жалилова С. Использование лингвокультурологического подхода в обучении иностранным языкам //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 64-71.
5. Rixsibayevna D. S. TYPES OF LEARNING ENGLISH METHODS IN SPORT DIRECTION //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2024. – Т. 15. – №. 1. – С. 45-49.
6. Rixsibayevna D. S. IMPROVE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 531-534.
7. Rixsibayevna D. S. COMMUNICATIVE-COGNITIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES //World scientific research journal. – 2022. – Т. 4. – №. 1. – С. 198-200.
8. Максудова В. Х., Жалилова С. Р., Нуримова С. Э. КОММУНИКАТИВНО - КОГНИТИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД К ОБУЧЕНИЮ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ //Путь науки. – 2015. – №. 3. – С. 128-130.
9. Dereka. (2016). Current Trends in the Professional Training of Physical Education Professionals in the European Union. TG. Derek. Pedagogical Sciences,3(85),42-47.

10. Ferkins, L. (2012). God Boards are Strategic: What does that Mean for Sport Gormance. Lesley Ferkins. *Journal of Sport Management*, 26(1), 67-80.
11. Flavell, J. H. (1979). Meta-cognition and cognitive monitoring: a new area of cognitive-developmental inquiry. *American Psychologist*, 34(10), 906-911.
12. Flavell, J. H. (1997). Speculation about the nature and development of meta-cognition. In F. E. Weinert & R. H. Kluwe (Eds.), *Meta-cognition, motivation and understanding* (pp. 21-30). Erlbaum.
13. Jacobs, F. (2013). Making sence of teaching social and moral skills in physical education. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 18(1), 1-14.
14. Johnson, R. E., Chang, C-H. D., & Lord, R. G. (2006). Moving from cognition to behavior: What the research says. *Psychological Bulletin*, 132, 381-415.